

THE GREAT FRENCH BOURGEOIS REVOLUTION AND THE HISTORICAL SIGNIFICANCE OF THE "DECLARATION OF THE RIGHTS OF MAN AND CITIZEN"

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Abstract: The universal historical importance of the Great French bourgeois revolution of 1789, its place in the history of the whole world, the relevance of the ideas advanced by the revolution, as well as the content and historical importance of the adopted "Declaration of the Rights of Man and Citizen" form the basis of the lecture.

Keywords: France, revolution, National Assembly, development, declaration.

The revolution that took place in France at the end of the 18th century played a huge role in the country's subsequent history. He determined the revolutionary way of development of France, unlike another large European country - England. If the American Revolution that took place during this period was the first warning that the old feudal order was coming to an end, the French Revolution destroyed this order. The revolution was of universal importance, and it opened a new chapter in the history of European civilization. The ideas about human freedom and equality, which appeared during the revolution, echoed for a long time in Europe and America, Asia and Africa, and pushed humanity towards freedom. The ideas of Freedom, Equality and Fraternity of the revolutionary period gave a universal character and a great meaning to the struggle of many nations for their independence, including the modernist movement in Turkestan.

The revolution also shattered the pattern of religious tolerance in the new era. The National Assembly, by its decree of December 24, 1789, granted citizenship rights to Muslims along with representatives of all non-Catholic denominations, allowing them to hold civil and military positions¹.

The Great French Revolution began on July 14, 1789, and lasted until July 27, 1794, and even, according to some historians, until November 9, 1799, when Napoleon Bonaparte came to power. Alphonse Olar, the author of a number of studies on the French bourgeois revolution in the last quarter of the XIX century

¹ See: Прусская Е.А. Ислам во французской революции. О книге Йана Коллера. / Французкий ежегодник. 2022. С.403.

and the first quarter of the XX century, described this process in a logical way in his work entitled "Political History of the French Revolution": "I want to tell the political history of the French revolution from the point of view of the origin and development of democracy and the republic," he said.

"Democracy is the logical extension of the principle of equality; and the logical continuation of the principle of the supreme power of the people is the republic. These two outcomes do not occur simultaneously. In 1789, instead of democracy, the people established bourgeois regimes based on property censorship; Instead of a republic, they established a limited monarchy. It was not until August 10, 1792 that the French established a democratic system by recognizing universal suffrage; only on September 22, 1792, they destroyed the monarchy and established a republic. Regarding the republican form of government, it may be said that it existed until 1804, when the republican government was transferred to the hands of the emperor; as for democracy, it was abolished in 1795, when the constitution of the III year was introduced," he writes.

The well-known Russian historian A.D. Gradovsky focuses on the experience of the French Revolution and reveals its legal character. According to him, the French Revolution was a global historical process that began much earlier than the XVIII century and did not end only with the Great French Revolution. A.D. Gradovsky says that the roots of the French Revolution should be sought in the European Reformation process. The industrial revolution and political processes that started in England in the XVII century and America in the XVIII century also formed the basis of the French Revolution. The main reason for the backwardness of France, the most powerful country in Europe, but increasingly lagging behind in industrial development, was its political system, which did not meet the requirements of the new era. For this reason, "this process, which was of local importance in England and America, became of pan-European importance in and through France, which was able to generalize the new formulas and popularize them by any means"².

On August 26, 1789, the Constituent Assembly adopted the Declaration of the Rights of Man and Citizen. This Declaration is a logical continuation of the historical document adopted in North America on July 4, 1776 and founded the US state, and has gained historical significance on a global scale. This document consists of 17 articles, and in its 3rd article, it was declared that the nation is the

²См.: Градовский А.Д. Натурализм в истории. Собр. соч. Т. 3. – СПб., 1899. С. 536 – 537.

supreme source of power³. The document recognized human rights, equality, freedom and happiness of all citizens. Article 1 of it states: "People are born free and equal and remain so. "Social difference can be based only on common benefit," it was noted. The meaningful teachings of the Declaration do not resonate today as the only voice of a venerable past that should be remembered only in connection with the historical date. It has a great impact on the heart and consciousness of a modern person who has experienced the terrible disasters of the XX century and hopes to avoid new disasters⁴.

This document was a symbol of true courage and revolution in its time, and for more than 200 years it has been the basic body of law for European democrats and liberals. As a proof of this opinion, it should be said that this Declaration was reflected in the preambles of the constitutions adopted in 1791, 1793, 1795 in France. At the same time, the "Declaration of the Rights of Man and the Citizen" was used as the basis for the preamble of the constitutions of the Fourth Republic adopted in 1946 and the Fifth Republic developed in 1958⁵.

The "Declaration of Human and Civil Rights" and the "Declaration of Human Rights" adopted by the United Nations in December 1948 based on it, served as one of the fundamental foundations for many countries, including the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. For example, in Article 2 of the Declaration: "The purpose of any political union is to ensure the natural and inalienable rights of man. They include the rights to freedom, property, security, and resistance to tyranny," and Article 3: "The nation is the source of sovereign power.

Power, if it is not given by the nation, cannot be owned by any organization or single person", and the contents of these articles are in Article 7 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan adopted on December 8, 1992: "The people are the only source of state power", article 10: "Only the Oliy Majlis and the President of the Republic elected by the people of Uzbekistan can act on behalf of the people of Uzbekistan". Any part of the society, political party, public association, social movement or individual has no right to act on behalf of the people of Uzbekistan.

The Great French Revolution, especially the First Republic in France, has great historical significance. This revolution, called "The Great" by the left forces,

³ Les Constitutions de la France depuis 1789. – P., 1970. P. 33 – 34.

⁴ See: Киссель М.А. Принципы 1789 года (Генезис и первое применение). / Вопросы философии. № 10 1989. С. 73.

⁵ See: Les Constitutions de la France depuis 1789. – P., 1970. P. 371 – 374; Les institutions la Veme Republique – P., 1994. P. 18.

overthrew the old order not only in France, but also in the whole of Europe. It was of international importance, and the entire XIX century passed under its influence.

As a result of the revolution, a new society based on a market economy began to be built in France, the royal system, which was based on absolute rule and had existed for more than a thousand years, was overthrown and a republic was established. In France, society based on feudalism was put to an end.

The Great French Revolution was a democratic, people's revolution, in which the ideas of Equality, Liberty, Fraternity were spread throughout the world. The Great French Revolution abolished feudal orders, privileges and titles and opened the way for the rapid development of industry, commerce and agriculture.

As a result of the revolution, the adoption of the "Declaration of the Rights of Man and Citizen" by the Constituent Assembly on August 26, 1789, and the Constitution adopted by the Convention on September 3, 1791, are extremely important⁶. The elections held in the country on the basis of these documents raised the level of the political consciousness of the French people.

So, the Great French bourgeois revolution was a very important event in the history of the country. Due to the tradition started by this revolution, France chose the revolutionary path of capitalist development, and in order to move to a new stage of development, in most cases, it was forced to make a revolutionary restructuring of the political system.

The Great French Revolution was a turning point in the history of the whole world in a certain sense. The ideas he put forward - Freedom, Equality, Fraternity had a great impact on the further development not only of Europe, but also of the peoples of other continents.

Also, the history of the revolution has become a great lesson for many peoples who are on the threshold of the New Era. In it, the government's reliance on brute force, ruthless massacres, use of terror as a means of solving all problems, and the physical destruction of political opposition were the terrible realities that brought about the revolution.

⁶ Les Constitutions de la France depuis 1789. – P., 1970. P. 35 – 67, 79 – 92.

